

Deliverable 6.3

Business Models

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Deliverable Information

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Abstract (for public dissemination only)	Adoption of the GREAT approach and method depends on key actors understanding the costs and benefits which are implied. To this end, the potential business models that can be deployed are identified. A business model canvas and matrix have been created, which represents the value to stakeholders, the use of the technology and the outputs, highlighting the key components and variations. Options on models are explored including price points and value propositions.
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List of Abbreviations

BMC	Business Model Canvas
CA	Consortium Agreement
CAC	Customer Acquisition Cost
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
DEFRA	Department for Environment Food and Rural Affairs
DiBL	Dilemma Based Learning
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
DaaS	Data as a Service
EC	European Commission
EGE	The European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulations
GREAT	Games Realising Effective and Affective Transformation
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
LTV	Life Time Value
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
PM	PlayMob
PP	PlanetPlay
SaaS	Software as a Service
SGI	Serious Games Interactive
UNDP	United Nations Development Program
UK	United Kingdom
UKRI	United Kingdom Research & Innovation
WP	Work Package

1. Executive Summary

This deliverable summarises the research undertaken by the GREAT project in examining the business models applied in the use of games to link citizens in dialogue with policy makers examining policy dilemmas related to the climate change crisis.

The existing and current business models applied by the industrial partners SGI and PlanetPlay are examined using the combined lenses of three derivatives of the Business Model Canvas, the Value Proposition Canvas and the Lean Canvas.

This approach exposes the attributes of the partners' business models and provides formal conceptualisations of how these organisations function in an emerging domain of activity. The assumptions underlying the models, specifically the value propositions, are tested and evaluated in the GREAT case studies currently undertaken in the project's accompanying work package 4.

A number of alternative revenue models are considered, and informed by this analysis, and by contemporary business literature. We conducted in-depth interviews with the industrial partners – SGI and PlanetPlay, as well as GREAT stakeholder groups and sponsors to further develop the refined business models informed by our research.

This public report highlights the GREAT partners' research into the business aspects of the project. It is anticipated that the content will be of interest to a wider audience including the EU, games development studios, policy makers and potential sponsors of activities.

2. Introduction

This document has two distinct purposes: the first is to outline potential business models that are informed by the activities and outputs of the GREAT project, which the participating commercial partner could deploy. The second is to clarify the potential, costs, benefits and value of engagement with games as tools for linking key policy stakeholders, using business models to assess the use of technology and the value proposition offered by the GREAT methods and approaches. The project applies the Business Model Canvas and Lean Model Canvas as the primary, exploratory and investigative tools for highlighting key requirements, aspects and propositions.

The GREAT project employs two contrasting approaches to examine policy dilemmas related to climate change. These exemplify key perspectives and techniques that leverage game technology to engage players and expose their perspectives and views. The first approach, as applied by commercial partner Serious Games Interactive (SGI), involves facilitating serious games for stakeholders to assist them in identifying and exploring dilemmas presented within a particular area of climate change. The second, as applied by commercial partner PlanetPlay (PP), involves large-scale polling

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techniques embedded in-game environments to engage players in response to questions, with the potential to achieve global-scale engagement and produce large public open datasets for further or future examination. The two approaches can be combined effectively, for example, by exploring a dilemma with a serious game and then investigating particular aspects through embedded polling. These operational models are highlighted in this report, together with value propositions and perspectives for stakeholders including games developers, policy makers, and industry. We further explore the use of data within the business model planning process, which involves a delicate balance of ethics, access and economics. The business models and matrix can be extrapolated to define a potential GREAT project ecosystem involving sponsors, stakeholders, the games industry, policy makers and citizens.

The application of the business model process articulates the potential of the GREAT project in line with the expectations of the grant agreement to make a significant impact culturally, economically and on society. The document does not detail the exploitation strategy for project outputs, as detailed in the accompanying deliverable [D6.2 Dissemination and Exploitation Plan](#).

The purpose of this document is to formulate the business models, which have emerged from the GREAT project activities and highlight the associated business models of the GREAT project. To operationalise work on this report, two objectives have been defined:

1. **Objective One** is to identify and represent the business models of the GREAT industrial partners. These models will support the long-term sustainability of the outputs, as well as the continuous, effective use of the methodologies and technologies developed in the project thereby moving beyond state-of-the-art use of technology to inform priorities in policy making.
2. **Objective Two** is to gather a range of contextual business models from stakeholders engaged in the project to effectively illustrate the domain in which the GREAT project is situated. The stakeholders, together, form an ecosystem that includes games, game development companies, and policy-makers concerned with the effects of climate change.

The document's recommendations are informed by stakeholder consultation facilitated through the use of the business and value proposition canvas and the lean variant to characterise the approach and platform design. The proposed models will support the long-term viability, exploitation and sustainability of the GREAT outputs.

3. Business Modelling in the GREAT Project

The GREAT project has adopted a multi-disciplinary approach and model, the multi-disciplinary framework, to conduct its research (Hollins *et al.*, 2023), which involves critical analysis of multiple perspectives. This document examines business perspectives on the GREAT project through the well-established lens of Business Modelling. For this project, we have adopted the definition of Business Models proposed by (Massa *et al.*, 2016):

- Business Models as attributes of real firms.
- Business Models as cognitive/linguistic schemas.
- Business Models as formal conceptual representations of how a business functions.

It is critical, not just in terms of the sustainability and commercial exploitation of the GREAT outputs, that we understand the attributes and functions of industrial organisations involved in this emergent domain. It is with this aim that we have used established tools to provide a conceptual representation of the business activities of the industrial partners and the wider stakeholder groups engaged in the GREAT project and in the broader emerging business domain. The tools we have selected are:

- The Business Model Canvas (Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2010)
- The Value Proposition Canvas (Osterwalder *et al.*, 2014)
- Lean Start-up Canvas (Reis, 2011)

3.1 Business Model Canvas

The Business Model Canvas is a strategic management template providing a structured business model overview. It focuses on nine key building blocks:

1. Customer Segments: Defining the different groups of people or organisations an enterprise aims to reach and serve.
2. Value Propositions: Describing the bundle of products and services that create value for a specific customer segment.
3. Channels: Describing how a company communicates with and reaches its customer segments to deliver a value proposition.
4. Customer Relationships: Describing the types of relationships that a company establishes and maintains with specific customer segments.
5. Revenue Streams: Representing the cash that a company generates from each customer segment.

6. Key Resources: The most important assets required to make a business model work.
7. Key Activities: The most important actions a company must undertake to operate.
8. Key Partnerships: The network of suppliers and partners that make the business model work.
9. Cost Structure: All costs incurred to operate a business model.

The Business Model Canvas (BMC) was selected as the primary tool for analysis due to its accessibility and ease of use. This enables the project to capture business complexity in terms of well-defined characteristics, facilitating collaborative analysis with non-academic industrial partners and stakeholders. These tools enhance the project's capacity to conceive of sophisticated potential business models appropriate for the technically and politically complex environment in which the GREAT project is situated.

We recognise that the BMC has its critics (Verrue, 2014) regarding a perceived lack of consistency due to overlaps caused by the fixed nature of its architecture. However, the useability and depth of the BMC justify its use in the project. It is also recognised that the Value Proposition and Lean Canvases are both derivatives of the BMC. The Value Proposition Canvas elaborates on the value proposition segment of the BMC. The Lean Model and the BMC are valuable tools for understanding and structuring a business but have different focuses.

3.2 The Value Proposition Canvas

The Value Proposition canvas was developed from the Business Model Canvas but provides a different focussed perspective. It is a tool designed to aim to design products or services clearly positioned to respond to customers' values and needs to ensure a fit between the product and service and market.

The primary advantages of using the Value Proposition Canvas are:

1. It aims to provide a greater understanding of the customer's needs and expectations.
2. Aims to help develop products and services structured around identified customer requirements and needs.
3. Provides the ability to compare established products with these identified needs.
4. Provides an ability to analyse the product or service and market fit.

5. Helps avoid developing products and services that do not serve a customer base.
6. Can identify processes to save both time and money.

3.3 Lean Model

The Lean Model is a broader approach to business management that emphasises efficiency and eliminating waste. It focuses on creating value for the customer while minimising resource consumption. As described by Reis (2011), key principles include:

- Customer focus: Understanding and meeting customer needs.
- Value stream mapping: Identifying and eliminating waste in the value delivery process.
- Continuous improvement: Constantly seeking ways to enhance efficiency and quality.
- Just-in-time production: Producing goods or services only when needed.

The Key Distinctions between the models are:

- Scope: The Lean Model is a broader framework for managing an entire business, while the Business Model Canvas focuses specifically on the business model and the Value Proposition Canvas is focussed on market fit.
- Focus: The Lean Model emphasises efficiency and waste reduction, while the Business Model Canvas focuses on creating and capturing value.
- Level of Detail: The Lean Model is more conceptual and high-level, while the Business Model Canvas provides a detailed breakdown of a business model.

The Lean Model provides a broader philosophy for running a business, and is designed for businesses looking to improve overall efficiency, reduce costs, and enhance customer satisfaction. It can be applied to a business of any size. In contrast, the BMC is a tool for understanding and designing a business model, and is best used by start-ups and businesses undergoing significant transformation, helping to visualise and validate business concepts. Many businesses find value in using both approaches together to achieve their goals.

3.4 Research Data Gathering

The methodology applied in preparing this report has involved unstructured interviews and discussions with the two participant industry partners – SGI and Planet Play, with games development studios Sybo and Lockwood and interviews with the engaged

sponsors of the GREAT case study – UNDP and Waterwise. A further unstructured interview was undertaken with an independent organisation, the Open Data Innovation Team. The Open Innovation Team is a UK cross-government unit that works with experts to generate analysis and ideas for policy, helping colleagues review evidence, engage experts, develop policy and evaluate impact. Through university partnerships and training, they aim to help understand how organisations can work more effectively with the government.

The rationale for adopting an unstructured approach was to enable interviewees to respond without constraint and to ensure no confirmation bias was embedded in the models produced. Data collected in these interviews is used to populate the segments within each canvases.

- In-depth qualitative discussions and interviews with game development studio partners, including studio development partners – Lockwood and Sybo.
- In-depth qualitative discussions and interviews with GREAT industrial partners – SGI and Planet Play.
- In-depth discussions with the GREAT project sponsors – UNDP.
- Canvas workshop activity with industrial partners – SGI and PlanetPlay.
- Desk research on contemporary approaches to Business Modelling.
- In-depth interview with the Open Data Innovation team.
- In-depth qualitative discussions with ImpactInvest.org on policy interventions and modelling.
- Informed by the outcomes of the associated GREAT case studies undertaken in WP4.

4. Business Models – Discussion and Reflections

In this section, we highlight the existing business models and technologies deployed by the industrial partners of the GREAT project. We then examine and consider alternative potential transferable models and approaches currently deployed in related technological domains.

4.1 Current Business Models

The GREAT project has two industrial partners whose technologies and processes inform the project research methods. The business models these technologies and processes imply provide a baseline reference to how gaming and gaming technologies

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are currently leveraged to engage citizens and stakeholders in the development of climate change policy and priorities. Both industrial partners currently deploy highly innovative, though quite different, state-of-the-art methodologies, technologies and processes. Through them, they engage various stakeholders (such as citizens, pressure groups, policy makers and government) through gaming in exploring significant policy dilemmas. Both partner approaches are tested and validated within the GREAT project through a series of case studies on climate change policy, the design and methods of which are highlighted in the GREAT deliverables [D4.1](#) (Hollins *et al.*, 2023) and [D4.2](#) (Hollins *et al.*, 2024). The two industrial partner Baseline Business Models are provided below:

4.1.1 Serious Games Interactive (SGI) – Dilemma-Based Learning Model

The Dilemma Based Learning (DiBL) approach (DiBL, 2024) involves a mediated game used with small groups of stakeholders and a facilitator to gain perspectives on a particular issue by identifying and exploring a dilemma. The approach is consistent with contemporary citizen science methods of engaging citizens in scientific enquiry. DiBL is a platform used to create and deliver real-time active learning designs, including formats such as case studies, scenarios, dilemmas, micro-simulations, roleplay, and workshops. This enables facilitators, or in the GREAT context, sponsors to bring together multiple stakeholders in smaller, organised groups and input their feedback on a particular scenario to create a 'dilemma' to be addressed. For example, in GREAT Case Study 2 (GCS2) 'Waterwise', in the design phase at the time of writing, the scenario involves developing policies to tackle water shortages in the United Kingdom. The stakeholders invited to participate include the sponsor Waterwise, the private water companies, the Department for the Environment Food & Rural Affairs (DEFRA), industry and consumer/customer groups and associations, academics, scientists and specialists. The 'Sponsor' is the term applied in the project to the partner organisation owning the dilemma to be explored and subject to the GREAT case study. The dilemma presented involves the presentation of several scenarios involving saving water, for example, taking less time to wash or limiting the time of showers to less than four minutes. The participants worked through the dilemma learning whilst providing valuable insight and data to the sponsor of the activity, Waterwise.

The DiBL model involves both technology (the platform that is used to host the activity) and services (including consultancy, guidance and facilitation). The business model aims to have customers use the platform and services on a periodic basis, providing a learning experience for participants whilst providing a dynamic perspective of sentiment and opinion over time. This extended engagement provides deeper and more meaningful insights than can be obtained in a shorter interaction. The

longitudinal model and relationship also provide economies of scale to the sponsor of a DiBL game, resulting in cost benefits and a discount. The DiBL pricing model has several variables based on the number of users, the number of creators, i.e., someone with access to administer the DiBL process), the number of use cases, and the type of data, analytics and outputs required by the sponsor. A DiBL customer is typically an organisation in the EU that uses and/or delivers active learning around an open topic, often structured in a scenario with dilemmas. Participation in the GREAT project has provided opportunities to extend the application of DiBL to new areas of application in linking citizens and policy makers.

Price Points

The DiBL price points, as highlighted below, represent a software-as-a-service (SaaS) model enabling customers to have a simple option to get started (starter) and then three tiers of pricing based on the typical size of an organisation and how many users and usage would be required. The price point offers customers access to the software and data without ownership and an affordable opt-in/out model that supports budget control for both the customer and DiBL.

 Yearly Subscription

	STARTER	NORMAL	ORGANISATION	ENTERPRISE
Monthly Users*	500	1 000	3 000	6 000
Number of creators**	1	2	5	Unlimited
Active cases	2	6	20	Unlimited
Analytics	Simple	Advanced	Advanced	Advanced
Data export	-	Yes	Yes	Yes
Localization tool	-	-	-	Yes
Support	Email	Email	Email/Phone	Email/Phone
Price (monthly)	€160	€320	€495	Contact us
Disabled creator (discount)***	40%			
Extra creator	€ 40 pr. month			
Add 3000 monthly users	€ 120 pr. month			

Excl. VAT

* This is how many monthly users you have. The service won't stop working if you go a bit over the limit it.
 ** You can have unlimited non-creator users in the system.
 *** Available after minimum one year when cases are locked down.

Figure 1: DiBL Price Subscription Model.

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<p>PROBLEM</p> <p>Engage participants during facilitated events for active learning and real-time insights.</p>	<p>SOLUTION</p> <p>DiBL is a platform to create and deliver active learning with real-time insights including formats like cases, scenarios, dilemmas, micro-sims, roleplays and workshops that are instantly available.</p>	<p>UNIQUE VALUE PROP</p> <p>Empower organisations to create and deliver active learning and get real-time insights.</p>	<p>UNFAIR ADVANTAGE</p> <p>20 years experiences building similar formats that we now productivize.</p> <p>Major existing compay in related space.</p>	<p>CUSTOMER SEGMENTS</p> <p>Organisations in EU with a learning need within open topics.</p> <p>Education</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Higher education * NGOs / IGOs * Government / Muncipalties <p>Work</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Corporations * Training companies * Consulting companies
<p>EXISTING ALTERNATIVES</p> <p>Status Quo</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Powerpoints * Paper handout * Facilitator exercises * LMS solutions <p>Direct (Realtime audience tool)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Kahoot, Quizizz * MentiMeter, Woodlap * Bespoke solution 	<p>KEY METRICS</p> <p>North star</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * # of participants * # of active creators * # of active DiBL cases 	<p>HI-LVL CONCEPT</p> <p>Kahoot for dilemmas</p>	<p>CHANNELS</p> <p>Direct sales & marketing</p> <p>Thought leader & SoME</p> <p>Customers using solution</p> <p>Direct sign-up own web-site</p>	<p>EARLY ADOPTERS</p> <p>Organisations which DNA is to deliver active learning and/or covers open topics.</p> <p>Knowledge about facilitated learning, and existing alternative real-time audience interactions solutions in the markets (that doesn't get the job done).</p>
<p>COST STRUCTURE</p> <p>Employee salaries</p> <p>Marketing</p> <p>Hosting</p> <p>Admin cost</p>		<p>REVENUE STREAMS</p> <p>Yearly subscription</p> <p>Implementation services</p> <p>Content services</p>		

Figure 2: Lean Business Canvas: DiBL.

Value Proposition Canvas

Designed for:

DiBL

Designed by:

Simon Egenfeldt-Nielsen

Date:

22/07/2024

Version:

1.0

Design and Copyright by: Strategyzer AG (<https://www.strategyzer.com/>). PowerPoint implementation by: Neos Chronos Limited (<https://neoschronos.com>). PowerPoint implementation License: [CC BY-SA 3.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/3.0/)

Figure 3: Value Proposition: DiBL.

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4.1.2 PlanetPlay (PP) – Approach and Business Model

PlanetPlay takes questions, either produced by collaboration with the sponsor directly or embeds these questions into in-game surveys to engage a large-scale audience. This audience profile can be pre-defined, specifying a geographic context (global, a country, an area) or a demographic subset (through the choice of the game context). The PlanetPlay approach leverages existing popular games to reach millions of gamers globally, to provide data, insights and detailed analysis to policy makers. The approach and model involve three categories of stakeholder groups: *corporate entities*, *government* and *non-governmental organisations* (NGO).

Game studios generate engagement with the players their games attract. High-profile games are produced and managed by the developer, and this is where PlanetPlay embeds surveys to elicit feedback, sentiment and opinion from players. PlanetPlay believes that game studios are motivated to engage by their interest in their players' responses and playing community. One of the value propositions for the studios is acquiring a dataset which can represent an indication of player values. The company can leverage this for future commercial gain through content roadmaps, marketing or other activities. The motivation for leveraging games to gather values, sentiments and attitudes stems from an understanding that games are one of the most successful entertainment mediums of our time, with over 3 billion active players and revenues larger than the film and music industries combined. The medium has high engagement levels and facilitates two-way communication with its audiences, for example, by delivering studio messages and responding to behavioural characteristics exhibited by players through sophisticated analytical analysis. This rich opportunity for gathering data enables PlanetPlay to sell its services.

Games studios are becoming increasingly conscious of corporate social responsibilities (CSR). Jones (2013) provides an overview and reflections on the CSR agenda that some of the world's leading game companies are pursuing. This is evidenced by recent industry-led initiatives such as Playing for the Planet (Playing for the Planet, 2024), which provide further incentives for the studios to engage in activities that show the industry in a positive light. 2019 Planet Play (then Playmob) undertook a climate policy research study with the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). The project tested a 'playable advertisement' method - a paid-for advert placed within successful mobile games. Players were served an advert designed as an interactive quiz involving questions from various UNDP stakeholders.

Using this placement method, the revenue model for PlanetPlay consists of a monthly licence fee; scaled to the volume of the audience. The licence fee increases if a more bespoke solution is required with more specific targeted demographics. The variable costing model is related to the targeted media, as costs differ according to country, demographic and targeting. The more specific targeting, the more costly media would become. A second revenue model developed and currently being trialled in the GREAT case study 5 (GCS5) with UNDP involves directly engaging with game development studios to embed the activities within the game-playing experience. The initial findings of research within the GREAT project suggest that player engagement rates with the activity are much higher with this approach than with the in-game advertising approach detailed above. The revenue model will change as there are no increases in cost to the sponsor as the activity scales up.

Price Points

Figure 4 below highlights the Pricing Model that PlayMob (now PlanetPlay) applied. This model could be characterised conceptually as a data-as-a-service (DaaS) model with a clear focus on the value of the collection, curation and analysis of the data collected from players. Revenue is derived from a customer subscription, which provides the customer with access to templated surveys, distribution (via in-game ads and in-game hyperlinks) and access to the data collected, which PlayMob provides via a licence to the customer. The subscription cost depends on the volume of data collected due to the price sensitivity of scaling support. The price point is bespoke (between 5K [GBP] and 20K [GBP] per month) and varies depending on the status of the customer, with not-for-profit organisations benefiting from discounted rates. With PlayMob now part of PlanetPlay, price points are under review with an emphasis on open data, especially in support of the not-for-profit side. The GREAT project Business Model research will serve to inform the PlanetPlay Pricing Model options.

The GREAT project activities will produce a significant volume of Open Data. It is worth noting that in creating Open Data, this will impact on pricing and business Models, offering both threats to the existing models and opportunities to develop new models such as consultancy and software as a service model. These models will be further explored as the project progresses and will be embedded in the final exploitation plans of the project at a later stage.

Business MODEL

Figure 4: Playmob pricing model.

4.2 Exploration of Alternative Models

Thus far this document has examined and illustrated the models currently deployed by the two industrial partners in the GREAT project – SGI (DiBL) and PlanetPlay. There are, however, a number of alternative revenue and business models in scope that could be deployed by the GREAT industrial partners, or by new entrants into this emergent area of activity. Informed by interviews with the GREAT industrial partners (SGI and PlanetPlay), we discuss these alternatives, benefits and concerns and how they might be applied. The categories and characteristics detailed below have been developed, informed by existing models, as part of the GREAT project research activity.

4.2.1 Subscription-Based Model

Both GREAT platforms can work on a subscription-based model. Popular with clients or sponsors who want to spread and manage costs, a monthly fee based on usage enables the customers to scale up/down their service. In GREAT, customers could have a subscription to DiBL to run workshops/sessions to gain initial stakeholder insights and define/redefine the dilemma over time. PlanetPlay can then offer a subscription-based model to access data and insights, with a pricing model based on deeper insights and analytics.

- **Target Customers:** Game developers, publishers, marketers, and researchers who require ongoing access to comprehensive game data.
- **Value Proposition:** Offers tiered access to different levels of data granularity, analytics tools, and customization options. Higher tiers may include premium features like predictive analytics, competitive benchmarking, or personalised support.
- **Revenue Generation:** Recurring subscription fees based on the chosen tier and usage levels.

- **Benefits:** Predictable revenue stream, potential for high customer retention with valuable service.
- **Concerns:** Requires ongoing value demonstration to retain subscribers and competition from free or lower-priced alternatives.

4.2.2 Freemium Model

This model may be more applicable to PlanetPlay. However, DIBL could explore having an 'entry' free level or a 'try before you buy' model to enable customers to have a taster session before they commit to a premium service. For PlanetPlay and GREAT as a whole, potential not-for-profit customers may not have a budget to buy into new technology and services. Therefore, having free initial service access and if the service proves useful in solving a problem can result in a reduced fee for this type of stakeholder.

- **Target Customers:** A wider audience of game developers, enthusiasts, and smaller studios.
- **Value Proposition:** Offers a free tier with limited access to data and basic analytics, while a premium tier provides more in-depth analysis, advanced features, and larger data sets.
- **Revenue Generation:** Upsell free users to premium subscriptions and advertise on the free tier.
- **Benefits:** Large user base potential, easier customer acquisition.
- **Concerns:** Lower initial revenue requires a compelling value proposition to convert free users to paying customers.

4.2.3 Pay-Per-Insight Model

This model could have potential for GREAT and the two industrial partners. However, it would be challenging for start-ups because income streams are unpredictable. Nevertheless, this is an option for customers who wish to have specific insights, including data, analysed data, reports or briefings, and datasets, alongside customers who want a long-term view of data. A combination would balance the predictable and unpredictable and provide more certainty to the overall model.

- **Target Customers:** Game developers, publishers, and marketers seeking specific insights or data points for decision-making.
- **Value Proposition:** Offers on-demand access to specific datasets, custom reports, or targeted analysis.
- **Revenue Generation:** Charges per data request or report, potentially with volume discounts.
- **Benefits:** Flexibility for customers, potential for high-value transactions.
- **Concerns:** Less predictable revenue requires effective marketing to attract customers seeking specific insights.

4.2.4 Platform Licensing Model

Both SGI and PlanetPlay use the licensing model. The licencing model is one where the commercial companies charge sponsors or customers to access the technology platforms operated by the commercial companies. This could provide more outstanding direct agency to sponsors in controlling activities independently of the commercial provider. However, this model generates complexity regarding licence types, what is included, and the significant investment required to build, maintain, and drive sales.

- **Target Customers:** Larger game companies or platforms with internal data teams.
- **Value Proposition:** Licences the platform's technology and tools for internal use, potentially with customization and integration options.
- **Revenue Generation:** Licensing fees, ongoing support and maintenance fees.
- **Benefits:** High-value contracts, the potential for long-term partnerships.
- **Concerns:** Longer sales cycles require significant investment in platform development and customization.

4.2.5 Potential additional revenue streams

The combination of DiBL and PlanetPlay platforms is being tried and tested through the GREAT project. Although they both operate on their price points and model, the two can be combined to create one offering or an 'upsell' of each other's platforms to add value to them on their own. There is the potential to further develop revenue through what we will term 'premium services'. These would involve a subscription fee for access to advanced analytics to generate customised reports and priority access to activity support. Data licensing fees could be applied to the commercial use of data based on volume, industry or exclusivity. Consulting and support services present opportunities to charge for technical support, training, and technical advice. This model is discussed in the SGI summary (in section 5.1) described as the 'advantage' model. Consideration could be given to charging for targeted advertising or promoting complementary products and services.

4.2.6 Additional considerations

There are other considerations to be taken into account in developing business models. These include further exploitation of the value of the data generated by the GREAT activity to drive revenue. These could include working with game development studios and platform owners to provide access to exclusive data. This can add to the value proposition and attract additional customers. There is an opportunity to provide value-added services such as support and consulting services and data interpretation analysis services; these services can generate additional revenue streams and deepen customer relationships. It is not intended to make either commercial partners proprietary software or platforms available as 'Open Source' software. Though exemplars of

playable games, in the case of DIBL, are planned to be released soon to encourage enquiry.

4.3 Business Models for various stakeholder groups

This section considers the Business Models that apply to the various stakeholder groups engaging with the GREAT project. Whilst Business Models are usually applied to commercial companies, we have used the model to visualise the activities, functions and engagement models for sponsors and or stakeholders in the business ecosystem emerging because of the GREAT activities. This is aimed to provide multiple perspectives and dimensions on the business models deployed or under consideration and to enhance market understanding beyond that of the value proposition.

As detailed in section 2.1 of this document, we use the openly licenced tools – the Business Model Canvas (Osterwalder, 2010), the Value Proposition Canvas (Osterwalder *et al.*, 2014) and the Lean Start-up Canvas (Reis, 2011) variant of the Business Model Canvas to represent the stakeholder business models in a matrix relating to the GREAT project. The models provided in this section of the document are representative models for key stakeholder groups in the GREAT project. As detailed below, a Lean Canvas and Value Proposition Canvas are presented for each of the identified stakeholder groups.

Key identified Stakeholder Groups:

- The games development industry
- NGO/Not-for-profit Organisations
- Industry Alliance (Waterwise as a representative stakeholder sponsor and subject of GREAT Case Study 2 GCS2)
- Government and Policy Makers

4.3.1 Lean Canvas: Gaming Industry

The games development industry is a key stakeholder in the GREAT project. This business model is informed by in-depth, qualitative discussions and interviews with game development studio partners and GREAT industrial partners – SGI and Planet Play. Entertainment games (mobile, PC, Console) are the primary route through which the PlanetPlay approach can reach and engage with citizens. Surveys are embedded within these games as a hyperlink placed in editorial, messaging or visually, such as a green button. Alternatively, on PC and console games, a QR code can be placed in the game for the player to scan and open the survey on their mobile device. While these are straightforward mechanisms, PlanetPlay provides services and value with their expertise and deep understanding of the games development industry and market in collating, managing and analysing the data collected for stakeholders. It can be a highly effective tool for game studios. The players may develop a positive perception

of the studio by feeling that their voices and views are heard and be provided with an opportunity to provide input into policy. Players can speak up on climate change and feel heard.

The data generated can provide valuable insight into understanding players' sentiments, attitudes and motivations. The lean canvas below provides an overview of the game industry's opportunity to represent a model based on shared value. Based on this data, game studios can earn a royalty. However, this is predicated on sponsors or the private sector becoming willing to pay for valuable and trusted data, for example, to inform their 'green' product marketing campaigns.

<p>PROBLEM</p> <p>Little to no data on players climate attitudes Rising regulation requirements to be more sustainable Extremely long to-do lists and little time to action data or sustainability</p>	<p>SOLUTION</p> <p>In-game survey designed by experts, to ask players quickly how they feel about climate change Understanding what they can do in their games and as a studio, to comply to regulation while engaging players in the process - show they are taking action A simple solution which requires no integration into a game - simple link to add to editorial</p>	<p>UNIQUE VALUE PROPOSITION</p> <p>Engage deeply with your audience bu understanding their values and attitudes towards the environment</p>	<p>UNFAIR ADVANTAGE</p> <p>Partnership with the UN and Policy Makers 10+ years of connecting games to climate action Existing insight and data from UN, GGJ and other games x climate activations</p>	<p>CUSTOMER SEGMENTS</p> <p>Mobile games PC Games Console Games Games Platforms i.e. Unity</p>
<p>EXISTING ALTERNATIVES</p> <p>Survey Monkey Qualtrics Zoho</p>	<p>KEY METRICS</p> <p>Engagement % of survey completed Completion rates Click through rates</p>	<p>HIGH-LEVEL CONCEPT</p> <p>We are the data.ai for climate change.</p>	<p>CHANNELS</p> <p>Direct to studios Through groups and alliances such as P4P, UKIE, TIGA, NEO etc Major events; GDC, Gamescom, PG Connect, Develop, Games Beat, TGA/SGF,</p>	<p>EARLY ADOPTERS</p> <p>Games part of the Playing for the Planet Alliance and/or GGJ or other group Studios with a sustainability lead Studios who have done something 'green' before</p>
<p>COST STRUCTURE</p> <p>People Servers Tech stack</p>		<p>REVENUE STREAMS</p> <p>Shared value model - no cost to games studios - they provide access to gamers, we provide them the data back</p>		

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LEAN CANVAS

Figure 5: Lean Canvas: Gaming Industry.

4.3.2 Value Proposition: Gaming Industry

The games development industry is a key stakeholder in the GREAT project. This business model is informed by in-depth, qualitative discussions and interviews with game development studio partners and GREAT industrial partners – SGI and Planet

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Play. The value proposition for the game development studio represented below is twofold:

- Informed by data, gaining an improved understanding of their audience, which may ultimately drive deeper engagement with the game (which could result in increasing lifetime value and monetisation).
- Improved and visible Corporate and Social Responsibility activity.

The game development industry is proactively addressing its corporate and social responsibility. An example is the Association for UK Interactive Entertainment (UKIE) production of the Green Games Guide <https://ukie.org.uk/greengamesguide> and recent partnership with the United Nations Playing for the Planet initiative <https://www.playing4theplanet.org/>. In the future, a royalty model could provide revenue for game studios, providing access to their players and receiving a revenue share of any commercial arrangements from the aggregate data. For example, a brand may wish to learn more about the green attitudes of a specific demographic and would value the vast datasets that can be collected through gaming. Although the data collected is intended to inform policy, it could also inform commercial brand owners and other sectors on the attitudes and preferences on key issues of demographic groups globally.

Figure 6: Value Proposition: Gaming Industry.

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4.3.3 Lean Canvas: NGO/Not-for-Profit

Informed by in-depth qualitative discussions with GREAT stakeholders – UNDP, the Lean Canvas Business Model canvasses for a Non-Government Organisation (NGO) or not-for-profit, such as the United Nations, is provided in Figure 7. This group of stakeholders may have difficulty reaching and engaging large audiences, and in particular, in targeting groups such as millennials and Gen Z. Traditional methods can be costly and ineffective, for example, email surveys, survey tech, telephone interviews, etc.

Gaming is not necessarily the primary choice for this stakeholder group to understand citizens' views, as games can have negative connotations. As a result, gaming has historically not been seen as an effective communication tool. However, this is changing as further research is undertaken and as the result of generational change.

<p>PROBLEM</p> <p>Reaching the hard to reach Engaging people in complex decisions Reaching people globally at mass scale Engagement rates</p>	<p>SOLUTION</p> <p>Use existing games as a means to reach and engage In-game technology to talk to players (people/citizens) Simplify messaging into short quiz type experiences</p>	<p>UNIQUE VALUE PROPOSITION</p> <p>Engaging hard to reach and global audiences through gaming.</p>	<p>UNFAIR ADVANTAGE</p> <p>Direct partnerships with multiple major gaming studios. Existing knowledge and experience in impacting major decisions through insights from gamers (People's Climate Vote).</p>	<p>CUSTOMER SEGMENTS</p> <p>Policy makers NGOs Local Councils</p>
<p>EXISTING ALTERNATIVES</p> <p>Email surveys Phone surveys Doorstep/F2F Surveys</p>	<p>KEY METRICS</p> <p>Engagement Rate Completion Rate</p>	<p>HIGH-LEVEL CONCEPT</p> <p>PlanetPlay = Yougov for the next generation</p>	<p>CHANNELS</p> <p>Reaching audiences directly through major games titles Reach audiences through gaming communities (channels around games such as Discord, X, Facebook and TikTok)</p>	<p>EARLY ADOPTERS</p> <p>Have a priority area to gather public insight about Targeting hard to reach demographics Need insight for strategic planning and/or manifestos</p>
<p>COST STRUCTURE</p> <p>People Servers Other tech Services Media (potentially) for in-game ads</p>		<p>REVENUE STREAMS</p> <p>Licence fee (based on volume and scale) Media fee (% of media bought) Services - bespoke surveys, additional support</p>		

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LEAN CANVAS

Figure 7: Lean Canvas: NGO/Not-for-profits.

4.3.4 Value Proposition: NGO/Not-for-Profit

This business model is informed by in-depth qualitative discussions with GREAT stakeholders – UNDP. The Value Proposition model canvasses for a Non-Government Organisation (NGO) or not-for-profit, e.g., the United Nations, is provided in Figure 8. The value proposition for this group of stakeholders lies in access to a vast dataset from a demographic group that is often hard to reach.

This valuable information can then be used to inform policy at a speed and scale which was previously impossible to achieve. This is tangible value for this stakeholder group due to the urgency in the impact work that they exist to do. For this stakeholder group,

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the project will explore a reduced rate fee or free version, an open data model, which would also give stakeholders value but with no big budget commitment.

Figure 8: Value Proposition: NGO/Not-for-Profit .

4.3.5 Industry Alliance informed by Waterwise GCS2

Based on the preliminary findings of the GREAT Waterwise case study (GCS2), we examine the first 'end to end' solution, combining both the DiBL and PlanetPlay approaches, to develop a GREAT Business Model illustrated in figure 9.

The most challenging aspect of gaining meaningful data from large-scale sentiment analysis is to ensure that the questions used in any survey are rigorous, ethical, well-considered and constructed. To ensure this, sponsors need a deep understanding of the problem or dilemma, and the DiBL approach provides this rigour by enabling facilitated activities to elicit multi-stakeholder perspectives or citizen scientific approaches.

Informed by the DiBL approach to developing questions and dilemmas, the PlanetPlay approach is deployed to a wider audience. The resulting data can be analysed using a variety of proprietary tools, such as Microsoft Power BI and SPSS analytics, or open-source alternatives, such as R and Metabase.

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PROBLEM Difficult to reach and engage large volumes of hard to reach demographics Hard conversations to simplify Solidarity between stakeholders and agendas	SOLUTION Games reach 1 in 2 people in the UK and using a simple survey to reach people through games, where they are already Simplify conversations through easy to answer questions A small scale facilitated gaming experience to gain insights into perspectives and find a unified 'dilemma'	UNIQUE VALUE PROPOSITION Reach hard to reach people, on their terms, and understand what they really care about	UNFAIR ADVANTAGE Industry convener Trusted organisation Seat at the table for political influence and decision making	CUSTOMER SEGMENTS NGO/Charity Industry Alliances Government Organisations
	KEY METRICS Engagement Completion Click through rates		CHANNELS Industry Government	
EXISTING ALTERNATIVES Survey Monkey / email surveys Telephone surveys F2F surveys Surveys through social channels	HIGH-LEVEL CONCEPT Public polling for millennials and Gen z Stakeholder engagement to define problem areas	EARLY ADOPTERS Forward thinking with technology Big challenges which involve public opinion Priorities to engage public and stakeholders		
COST STRUCTURE People Servers Other tech stack costs		REVENUE STREAMS Licence fee Media buy fee Consultancy - bespoke support		

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LEAN CANVAS

Figure 9: Lean Canvas: Industry Alliance.

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Figure 10: Value Proposition: Industry Alliance.

4.3.6 Government and Policy Makers

Government and policy makers are key beneficiaries of the outputs of the GREAT project, specifically in understanding the emergent ecosystem for the products and services subject to research and development are undertaken in the GREAT project. Whilst Government and policy-makers are not focussed on the 'business' aspects of the project, it is worthwhile to highlight their role in the emergent ecosystem as beneficiaries, and this is highlighted using the 'business model canvas to ensure visual consistency with other key stakeholders of the ecosystem the model provides a representation of how Government and policy makers can benefit, or the value proposition to these key stakeholders.

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Figure 11: Government & Policy Makers Business Model Canvas.

5. The Business Model Matrix

This section focuses on the customer segments and value proposition for stakeholders and sponsors engaging with the GREAT industrial partners – SGI and PlanetPlay. These are summarised in the Business Model Matrix table below. We define customer/sponsor as an organisation that benefits from using the technology and methodologies to address a specific challenge or dilemma. The GREAT project is complex and involves interactions with multiple stakeholders with the potential of engaging both paying and non-paying customers. The Business Model Matrix in Table I below highlights the four key stakeholder groups, which will interact with the methodology developed within the GREAT project. These are businesses, games studios, government/policy/NGO and citizens.

Target Customer / Sponsor Segments	Value Proposition
<p>Businesses: Large and small companies across various industries seeking data-driven insights. For example, an FMCG (Fast Moving Consumable Goods) business wishing to better understand their customer demographic's attitudes towards climate change, to better communicate and position their own green actions as a brand. Such as, a kitchen roll brand who has to communicate a sustainability message to a particular demographic and needs to be able to have insight in order to do so. With a hard-to-reach demographic that they know are playing games (millennials, Hispanic, US-based) a platform like this would give them access to the information required.</p>	<p>For Businesses: Access to high-quality, reliable open data to inform decision-making, improve operational efficiency, and drive innovation. The data is at a very large scale and accesses hard to reach audiences, consequently not only be quality, but in some instances, unique or hard to obtain for certain businesses. Having a constant flow of this insight will enable business to add more relevant message and optimise as they learn more about their customers attitudes and sentiment.</p>
<p>Games Studios: All games studios, who are prioritising their impact on the planet, and address a demographic that cares deeply about climate change and taking action. Studios will range across platforms (mobile, PC, console and VR), and games platforms such as Unity.</p>	<p>For Games Studios: In-game survey tools to access their players, API, dashboard or similar, to provide data back in a seamless way - no tech integration which saves games studios time and concern, simply a link placed in-game. This simple technology and methodology will give a constant flow of data which can be leveraged to inform green content strategies and engage players in climate action. There are two fundamental values here; 1) engaging deeply with the player base (thus monetising) and 2) actioning sustainability goals as a game and games studio.</p>
<p>Governments/Policy/NGO: Local, regional, and national government agencies committed to climate change and orchestrating policies that support reducing carbon emissions, cleaning and greening the planet. The GREAT models and approaches could be applied by sponsors /stakeholders to multiple topics and themes. Climate Change is identified as an exemplar that can be easily adopted as required.</p>	<p>For Governments/Policy/NGO: A platform to publish and share data, this may be in report format, a dashboard, or an API to pull data into their existing data sets. Getting the data to this segment in a useful way enables big data to become 'small data' which is actionable. The platform will enable stakeholders to speak up about the priorities in their view, to then narrow down on dilemmas and finally reach hard to reach audiences that this segment are finding it progressively more difficult to engage with.</p>
<p>Citizens: Individuals interested in accessing and using open data for personal or professional purposes.</p>	<p>For Citizens: Improved access to information, greater transparency, and opportunities to participate in civic life/have their opinions heard on an important topic, climate change. It may also enable a building of trust between citizens and decision makers, whereas before it has been opaque and in some cases not reliable.</p>

6. Potential Business Models for GREAT

The GREAT project business research activity has shown that the two industrial partners have quite distinct business models incorporating different value propositions. Given this, it is not appropriate to propose a single Business Model in a market that is still emerging, both in terms of technology and in terms of customer demand. It is in this context that we discuss what both organisations have learned both in the research and analysis underpinning this deliverable and the associated GREAT case studies.

6.1 SGI DIBL

As illustrated in the Value Proposition Canvas, DiBL has a unique value proposition that provides a real-time space for informed conversations between policy makers and citizens. The DiBL proposition has been extensively trialled and tested within the GREAT case study program specifically in the Waterwise case study (GCS2), the Green Jobs case study (GCS3) and the Rooftop Revolution (GCS4).

Initially, the DiBL proposition involved the provision of a self-service platform for sponsors or policy makers, but case study activities and evaluation have shown that this proposition has limitations. Very few sponsors and policy-makers have the capacity or capabilities (human and technical) to manage the processes involved in establishing the focus of the dilemma, establishing and managing the DIBL process, and delivering the activity to their constituents.

Even if the sponsors or policy makers were to have the capacity and capability, this would still result in a limited market as a classic 'platform only' approach. The GREAT case studies have revealed a significant requirement and dependency on what we describe as content and implementation services.

Content Services relate to creating narrative and game-like formats to prompt discussion amongst sponsor stakeholders, supplemented with support on the visual aspects of the DIBL through the creation of visual content, imagery or simple animations. Enhancing the visual aspects or increasing the fidelity would result in prohibitive cost increases that would limit the potential for this new market.

Implementation Services involve delegation of responsibility to customers, which has been challenging as the sponsors or policy-makers do not have the skills and capability to establish or distribute the DiBL activity. In this business model, sponsor stakeholders have access to an item bank of content containing materials and detailed information on the sponsors / policy makers' key dilemmas and messages to gather insight, which

is then provided back to the sponsor / policy maker. For example, in the Green Jobs case study (GCS3) situated in Austria, the initial concept was to develop an experience where the sponsor or policy maker invested in creating a DiBL that could be used in schools as a way to both communicate a message to students to gather their responses

which would be used to inform the Austrian government ministry concerned. In the Rooftop Revolution case study (GCS4), situated in Cyprus with an NGO called Urban Gorillas (<https://urbangorillas.org/about/>), a DiBL experience was created that facilitators could deploy in face-to-face workshops to prompt stakeholder discussion and reflection, and the insights and data gained were automatically gathered in the technical platform. In this example, the DiBL created value from multi-stakeholder perspectives: the users or students, the enabler, the teachers concerned and the creator sponsor or policy-maker. In both cases, the envisioned process or model was based on the assumption that the sponsor or policy maker had the skills, capacity and capability to manage the entire DiBL process from end to end, and this was not the case. This indicated that a detailed assessment of organisational capacity and ability should be undertaken as part of the customer segmentation. In reality, sponsors generally have only a subset of the capabilities required to undertake DiBL activities. Their workflows can be characterised as being on a project-by-project basis. This situation challenges the viability of a subscription-based model or a recurring fee for the platform to undertake regular updates. The sponsor still requires the platform to offer DiBL to users to communicate and gather data, provide ongoing access and support to the data, and change, reuse or repurpose existing content instead of creating entirely new DiBL games. SGI is working on lowering the entry barriers by making tools more straightforward to use and developing templates instead of entirely bespoke solutions.

This experience suggests a revised or emergent model for DiBL for the policy-making customer segment, one where dedicated or bespoke services are tailored to their individual requirements, capacity and capability supplemented by an ongoing subscription for the technology i.e. the DiBL platform. Historically, start-ups have veered away from the model suggested above as profitability has been identified in a classic business-to-business software-as-a-service (SAAS) type model with a focus on the easily scalable part of the offer being the technology and platform supplied to the user as an ongoing subscription-base model or where a yearly fee is paid (Giese & Hilpert, 2021). However, recently, there has emerged an appreciation of what is termed 'camels over unicorns' (Lazarow, 2020), referring to the adoption of the pragmatic and functional over the attractive and opening up an 'advantage' model that incorporates aspects of both ongoing charges and recurring service, maintenance and support (Giese & Hilpert, 2021). The advantage referred to is that businesses can

recoup their initial Customer Acquisition Cost (CAC) through the service and support aspects, and the remaining Lifetime Value (LTV) is gained through the classic business-to-business model with the potential for additional sales as new projects emerge from the sponsors. This model is especially attractive to SGI as they have a long history of delivering consulting services, which can differentiate them from other offers with only a platform-as-a-service approach.

Future Work

As the GREAT project progresses, further evaluation of these approaches will be undertaken for the DIBL model with a specific focus on the sponsor/ policy maker customer segment but more broadly over the other segments of the model should the need arise. The advantage model is potentially scalable not just in the GREAT project context but more broadly across other game development domains operating a business-to-business model or working-for-hire type arrangements, opening up opportunities to develop further revenue streams and long-term relationships through operating the advantage model described above.

6.2 PlanetPlay

The PlanetPlay approach offers a way to engage with global citizens at a mass scale through existing successful games, specifically mobile games, to engage players with surveys in exchange for an in-game reward. Where previously PlanetPlay leveraged in-game advertising placements to engage gamers, the GREAT project has enabled PlanetPlay to test extensively a way to reach and engage players through in-game hyperlinks. Both methods are deployed in the GREAT project; for example, GCS2 Waterwise will deploy in-game ads, whilst GCS1 UNDP trialled the in-game hyperlink. For both methods, data is curated consistently. There are three components to the PlanetPlay approach, which have been characterised as *Surveys*, *Distribution* and *Data*.

- Surveys are created from a templated survey tool. This has been designed for a maximum number of ten multiple-choice questions with both single-response or multiple-response options. The survey incorporates demographic data capture. Where questions are fact-based, points can be attributed to show players their scores. There is an option to provide bespoke surveys incorporating engaging ways to gamify the surveys. Bespoke templates could be offered, incorporating branded colours and logos, for an additional cost.
- Distribution - There are two methods of distribution:
Firstly, via in-game ads, which is costly; however, the benefit of this methodology is that detailed targeting can be applied. For example, with Waterwise, we have targeted a specific audience to their postcode. Therefore,

if specific demographic groups, such as age, gender, socioeconomic status, education level, etc., are required, this can easily be accommodated.

The second option is an in-game hyperlink, which was trialled in GCS1 UNDP. The link for the survey is placed in-game, such as a message, events system, player chat box, a pop-up message, loading screen or even an airship (as suggested by Pokemon GO!). Players click on the survey, complete the questions, and receive an in-game reward. The player would then go back to playing their game, ensuring that the quality of the experience was maintained and that the player would be focused on the game for a short time.

- Data - the data generated has multiple uses and values for different stakeholders. For games studios providing access to their player base, the value exchange is through providing them with analysed data from their players, allowing them to understand their player's sentiments and attitudes towards climate change. This enables the games studio to refine its green content roadmap to engage its players deeply. This feature has significant value to studios. The data is also valuable to stakeholder groups such as governments tasked with making decisions on policy change, businesses making decisions on areas such as communications for their products to customers, and NGOs who wish to influence policy and work with governments to inform their decisions. The GREAT project research has facilitated the development of improved data user interfaces, including dashboards and exploration of API to draw data for stakeholders' use. These improved data services provide the opportunity to develop chargeable services.

Future Work

The research undertaken in the GREAT project has provided the opportunity to further the business offerings of the industrial partners, specifically in the collection, curation and analysis of data. As the GREAT project progresses, further evaluation of these approaches will be undertaken for the PlanetPlay approach, specifically focusing on the Value Proposition offered to customers, stakeholders and sponsors related to data and analytic services. As GREAT develops, so will each of the areas above, whether it be redesigning the survey system, which could also open up new revenue streams with a selection of survey types, the distribution types will also widen as more games studios come on board and work with us to understand better where and how in-game links can be placed and even potentially automated to enable PlanetPlay to notify studios when a new survey is 'live automatically'. And finally, the data side will be a key element in terms of usage and price points, mainly for governments, NGOs and businesses. However, there could be a way to provide a royalty back to game studios based on a fee for data access. This could

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be a very interesting model as it is an untapped revenue stream back into games studios. It could open up more data frequently if their shared value becomes monetary.

6.3 The GREAT Exploitable Outputs

The associated GREAT project (revised) deliverable ([D6.2 Dissemination and Exploitation Plan](#)) deals directly with the dissemination and exploitation aspects of the project outputs. However, it is recognised of the impact of these activities on the business models included within this document. These will be refined iteratively as the project progresses. In this respect, the GREAT project has engaged directly with the Horizon booster service. The service is an initiative from the European Commission that provides services to EU-funded projects to help navigate the complexities of dissemination and exploitation.

The Link to the Booster service: <https://www.horizonresultsbooster.eu/>

The document ([D6.2 Dissemination and Exploitation Plan](#)) provides clear distinctions between communication – wide dissemination of the project and its outputs, dissemination of targeted communication to those groups who may benefit directly from the work undertaken in the project and Exploitation, how and by whom the outputs of the project will be used directly.

Booster's services encompass everything from dissemination and go-to-market strategies to advancing results towards market readiness. The service is providing support to complement and supplement the work undertaken here with respect to business models. Booster provided the initial business modelling advice.

As the project works over the period of the project, the GREAT business models will be developed informed by the service's work in this respect, and these will be represented in future updates of the dissemination and Exploitation strategy.

7. Conclusions

This deliverable has highlighted the business models applied by the GREAT industrial partners (objective 1). Informed by qualitative interviews, desk research, and the GREAT Case Studies, the project team has explored alternative business and revenue models with a view to the long-term sustainability of project outputs, the future development of the industrial partners and the long-term sustainability of the project outcomes, (objective 2).

Our research has exposed both deficiencies and merits of the existing models and has supported the trialling of new approaches and models, for example, in partnering game studios with a new value proposition recognising CSR as a key driver to engaging with the industry. The models and approaches discussed in this deliverable will be subject

to ongoing evaluation and further testing as the GREAT project and, more specifically, the case study research progresses with a view to informing the final Sustainability Strategy (D6.5) in month 36 of the project. The project research team will also continue to explore the potential of linking the two approaches modelled, DIBL and PlanetPlay, into one seamless end-to-end integrated value proposition and how this solution might be presented to future sponsors.

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